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Operational Resilience of Photovoltaic Systems to Heatwaves in Iberia

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Operational Resilience of Photovoltaic Systems to Heatwaves in Iberia

Abstract

Purpose: This study quantifies heatwave impacts on operational performance of Iberian photovoltaic (PV) plants in the context of climate change and examines whether typical meteorological year (TMY) based expectations mask event-driven losses. The study isolates performance ratio (PR) degradation, timing and recovery, providing evidence to align PV deployment planning and plants' operation and maintenance (O&M) with a warming climate.

Methodology: Three plants (Spain:2, Portugal:1) are analysed at hourly and daily scales across pre/during/post heatwave windows. PVsyst simulations are produced with typical meteorological year (TMY) and ERA5-Land. ERA5-Land is benchmarked to a co-located station. Resilience metrics are defined and analysed: PR drop, time-to-trough, recovery-to-90% and energy not served (ENS).

Findings: Heatwaves caused sharp hourly troughs (max 90.44%) but modest daily losses (the largest was 17.59%, Zebro-2P) with recovery within 0-1 days. TMY expectations overpredicted energy in all cases; the largest gap was 553.25 kWh (36.88 kWh/kWp; 17.3% of simulated energy) at Zebro-2P; the highest relative gap was 22.34% at Ariza-2S.

Research limitations/implications: Limited to three plants and four events, with in-situ meteorology at one site.

Originality: Introduces an auditable, event-centric PR stress test using in-situ-validated ERA5 denominators, contrasting TMY counterfactuals, with drop/time-to-trough/recovery metrics and an ENS design-gap to translate heatwave impacts into operationally actionable insights for resilient PV design and O&M.

Keywords: climate change, heatwaves, operational resilience, performance ratio, photovoltaics, typical meteorological year.

1. Introduction

1.1 Climate change and energy systems in Europe

The ongoing climate change is already having significant impacts in all aspects of human life, with Europe at the epicentre of its impacts. Since 1979, Europe's surface air temperatures have increased about three times as fast as the global average, in both winter and summer (Dong and Sutton, 2025). This excess warming is largely due to greenhouse gas emissions, changes in aerosols, and shifts in atmospheric circulation patterns that bring more warm air into Europe (Dong and Sutton, 2025; Vautard et al., 2023). Regional projections confirm European land temperatures will continue to rise by 1.2–3.4 °C under SSP1-2.6 and up to 8.5 °C under SSP5-8.5 by 2100, with the strongest warming expected in northeastern Europe and inland areas of Mediterranean countries (EEA, 2025).

As a result, the frequency, intensity, and duration of extreme weather events, including heatwaves, floods, droughts, hailstorms, wildfires, and high wind events, has increased (Vautard et al., 2023; Ruosteenoja et al., 2023). The 2022 summer was Europe's hottest summer, triggering the most severe drought in 500 years and widespread wildfires across

1
2
3 Southern Europe (Germanwatch, 2025; IPCC, 2022). Future projections indicate higher risks
4 of pluvial flooding in Northern and Western-Central Europe, while Southern and Western-
5 Central regions will face more frequent droughts and extreme heat, with populations enduring
6 over 60 days annually above 35 °C by century's end (IPCC, 2022).

7
8 Other hazards are also intensifying. Hail is already among the costliest weather-related
9 events, with northern Italy recording up to 40 severe storms per 10,000 km² each year (EEA,
10 2021; Kahraman, 2024). Climate simulations suggest hailstorm tracks could expand by 15–
11 30%, with doubled frequency of >50 mm hailstones (Brennan et al., 2025). Altogether, the
12 financial burden of climate-related risks in Europe could reach €40 billion annually by the
13 2080s, with €35 billion attributable to heatwaves and droughts (IPCC, 2022).

14
15 These changes already threaten energy infrastructure. Extreme events can reduce system
16 reliability by up to 16% and grid integration capacity by 34% (Perera et al., 2020). Both
17 centralised and distributed generation are vulnerable, with building-level PV systems
18 especially exposed during prolonged heatwaves or islanded operation (Han et al., 2025). The
19 economic losses amount to billions annually (Añel et al., 2024), with low-income households
20 disproportionately affected by energy poverty and price volatility (Lei and Xu, 2024).
21
22
23

24 **1.2 Photovoltaics as solution and vulnerability**

25 Solar photovoltaics (PV) play a dual role in Europe's energy transition: they are central to
26 decarbonisation, with more than 339 GW installed by 2024 (IEA, 2025), yet are also highly
27 exposed to climatic stressors. PV performance is sensitive to temperature, irradiance,
28 aerosols, humidity, and wind, many of which are shifting under climate change (Patt et al.,
29 2013; Bamisile et al., 2025).

30
31 Temperature is one of the most critical factors. Rising air temperatures reduce efficiency by
32 0.3–0.5% per °C above 25°C (IEA, 2022), while heatwaves can drive module surface
33 temperatures above 70°C, accelerating degradation (Islam et al., 2024; Omazic et al., 2019).
34 Laboratory studies show crystalline silicon modules lose 0.46–0.50% efficiency per °C, with
35 heatwave conditions leading to 4–10% efficiency drops between 35–49°C (Razak et al., 2016;
36 Hudişteanu et al., 2024). Thin-film technologies such as CIGS (Copper Indium Gallium
37 Selenide) are less thermally sensitive, offering some advantages in very hot regions (Ebhot
38 & Tabakov, 2022).

39
40 Thermal stress also affects other system components. Expansion mismatches between
41 polymers and encapsulants promote delamination and cracking (Meslier et al., 2024).
42 Inverters can derate or shut down once internal temperatures exceed design thresholds (De
43 Lima et al., 2023), while mounting structures deform under prolonged heat (Okonkwo et al.,
44 2025). Storage systems face reduced efficiency under elevated temperatures (Husain et al.,
45 2024).
46
47

48 Beyond heat, PV systems are vulnerable to other extreme events. Hail can cause direct glass
49 and cell damage, with losses up to 21.8% in thin-glass modules (Chakraborty et al., 2023).
50 Strong winds exceeding 200 km/h have detached modules from mounting structures, as
51 observed in northern Italy, Slovenia, and Croatia (Bošnjaković et al., 2023). Conversely,
52 moderate winds provide cooling benefits, lowering module temperature by 1–7 °C depending
53 on speed (Ataman et al., 2024). Flooding of ground-mounted systems can erode foundations
54 and damage electrical components, while dust storms increase module temperatures by 5°C
55 and reduce efficiency by 25% after 30 days without cleaning, though up to 90% can be
56 recovered after washing (Chen et al., 2019). Wildfire smoke reduces irradiance significantly,
57 cutting direct normal irradiance (DNI) by up to 42% and global horizontal irradiance (GHI) by
58
59
60

up to 17% (Corwin et al., 2025), while increased soiling due to ash accumulation or direct infrastructure damage also affect photovoltaic systems (Gilletly, 2023; Ford, 2024).

These stressors also accelerate long-term degradation. Elevated temperatures, UV radiation, and arid conditions degrade cables, seals, and junction boxes, even when certified for outdoor exposure (IEA, 2022). Prolonged operation above 85°C risks irreversible damage to modules (Gahlot, 2024). In southern Spain and Portugal, degradation rates reach up to 0.8% per year (Ascencio-Vásquez et al., 2019; Poddar et al., 2024). Altogether, these factors compromise both short-term yield and system lifespan, highlighting the need for resilient design and adaptive operation and maintenance.

1.3 Modelling gaps and resilience frameworks

Despite the growing risks posed by climate extremes, a substantial gap persists between model-based climate projections and the operational performance of PV systems under stress. The most widely used input for PV yield simulations remains the Typical Meteorological Year (TMY), which condenses long-term averages into a representative year. While useful for estimating typical annual production, TMY files cannot capture short-term anomalies or the dynamics of extreme events such as heatwaves, dust intrusions or wildfire smoke (Loon et al., 2020). As a result, TMY-based simulations often overestimate energy yield and underestimate operational risk. Similarly, many techno-economic models fail to incorporate degradation, soiling, or maintenance failures triggered by climatic stressors, further limiting their ability to inform adaptation planning (Hameed et al., 2024).

In response, recent literature emphasises the need for a more integrated perspective, bridging climate science, PV modelling and real-world performance analysis. This is reflected in the evolving paradigm of climate resilience, which stresses that solar infrastructure must not only be efficient under average conditions but also capable of withstanding and recovering from disruptive events (IEA, 2022).

The concept of resilience in the PV context is commonly articulated along three dimensions (Bošnjaković et al., 2023; Jimba et al., 2025):

- Resistance – the capacity of components (modules, structures, cabling) to withstand climatic stress without damage, such as hail, wind or extreme heat.
- Robustness – the ability to maintain stable operational performance under adverse conditions, such as inverter operation during high ambient temperatures or energy generation under dusty or smoky skies.
- Recovery – the speed and effectiveness with which a system can return to pre-event performance levels after disturbances such as floods, storms or wildfires.

Building on this conceptual framing, several methodological approaches have been developed:

- Simulation models, often TMY-based, remain the standard but are increasingly complemented by high-resolution climate projections (CMIP6, CORDEX) to better reflect future extremes (Rady et al., 2025; Rettie et al., 2023; Gutowski et al., 2020).
- Empirical and data-driven studies combine PV output with meteorological observations or reanalysis datasets such as ERA5-Land, enabling direct evaluation of system behaviour during actual events. Techniques range from statistical correlation models (Kim et al., 2019; Fregosi and Bolen, 2022) to advanced machine learning (Sun et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2023; Golam et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2024) and digital twin approaches (Pierce et al., 2024).
- Resilience metrics and indicators capture the dynamics of stress and recovery. These include resilience curves (Panteli et al., 2017; Dehghani et al., 2023), outage frequency

1
2
3 and duration (Ekisheva et al., 2022; Abdelmalak et al., 2023), restoration rates,
4 composite indices (Dwivedi et al., 2025; Ghosh and De, 2022) and survivability metrics
5 estimating the probability of maintaining critical loads (Pizzimbone and Jrad, 2023).
6

7 While these advances represent important progress, most existing frameworks remain limited
8 in addressing compound or sequential hazards which are increasingly common under climate
9 change. Bridging this gap requires methodological innovation, region-specific calibration,
10 improved access to high-resolution data, and stronger integration of simulations with
11 operational evidence.
12

14 **1.4 Operational and maintenance strategies for resilience**

15 As the frequency and intensity of climatic extremes increase, operation and maintenance
16 (O&M) practices become central to the resilience of PV systems. Traditional O&M frameworks,
17 designed for relatively stable conditions, are insufficient when plants are exposed to
18 heatwaves, floods, dust storms, hail, and high winds. Preventive strategies, site-specific
19 adaptation, and rapid response protocols are essential to safeguard long-term reliability (IEA,
20 2022).
21

22 Resilient O&M involves not only regular monitoring and inspections, such as infrared
23 thermography, I–V curve testing, and insulation quality assessments, but also the proactive
24 use of early anomaly detection systems. Beyond monitoring, resilience depends on the
25 availability of robust spare-part inventories, adaptive maintenance teams, and design
26 provisions that enable rapid recovery after disruptions (IEA, 2022).
27

28 Adaptation must also be context specific. In hot and arid regions, failures are commonly
29 caused by high temperatures, strong irradiation, and dry conditions; preventive actions include
30 shielding cables from direct exposure, replacing seals regularly, and using metal rather than
31 plastic ties. In humid and desert climates, operators face challenges such as potential-induced
32 degradation and accelerated wear due to rapid temperature fluctuations; recommended
33 practices include adjusting inverter settings to local conditions, improving ventilation, and
34 frequent filter cleaning (IEA, 2022). In flood-prone areas, elevation of inverters and combiner
35 boxes, IP67-rated materials, reinforced foundations, and drainage provisions are key to
36 minimising water ingress and hotspot formation. In cyclone- and storm-prone regions, survival
37 depends on dynamic wind load design, reinforced mounting structures, and strict quality
38 control during construction.
39

40 Across these contexts, a consistent lesson emerges: resilient PV operation is no longer
41 optional. Extreme weather increasingly shapes the operational reality of European PV plants,
42 requiring O&M strategies to evolve from routine maintenance to climate-adaptive asset
43 management. The challenge is not only to minimise downtime or repair costs, but to ensure
44 that PV generation remains a reliable pillar of Europe's decarbonisation goals under worsening
45 climate stress.
46

51 **1.5 Objectives and structure of the paper**

52 The aim of this paper is to quantify the impact of heatwaves on the operational performance
53 of photovoltaic plants in Southern Europe, focusing on Portugal and Spain. The analysis
54 compares measured performance ratios (PR) before, during and after heatwave events with
55 PVsyst simulations based on two meteorological inputs: the TMY and the ERA5-Land
56 reanalysis dataset. The study quantifies heatwave impacts on PV performance in Portugal
57 and Spain by comparing observed PR to PVsyst simulations driven by TMY and ERA5-Land,
58 highlighting event-driven losses, limitations of TMY for design under climate change, and the
59 added value of reanalysis. By bridging real-world evidence with simulation outputs, the study
60

contributes to the ongoing discussion on how to integrate climate resilience into PV planning and operation in Europe. The article is organised as follows. Section 2 describes the methodological framework, including data selection and simulation procedures. Section 3 presents the case study results, comparing observed and simulated PR values across different sites. Section 4 concludes with the main findings and recommendations.

2. Methodology

In this section datasets and procedures used in this work, such as heatwave selection and analysis, ERA5-Land benchmarking, PVsyst setups, and metric definitions, are presented.

2.1. Sites and datasets

Hourly production data from small/medium-scale PV plants in Southern Europe are used: one in Portugal and two in Spain as shown in Figure 1. Plant characteristics are shown in Table I.

Figure1

TableI

GHI and air temperature at 2m time series were extracted from the ERA5-Land (C3S, 2019) reanalysis with hourly resolution and for the grid point closest to the power plant sites. GHI and air temperature for the Amibil site were also available, from a SIAR (Sistema de Información Agroclimática para el Regadío, n.d.) meteorological station. All series are time-zone harmonized (DST-aware). GHI and production data with ERA5-Land GHI<100W/m² are excluded. The data from July 28, 2024, and July 29, 2024, were excluded in Ariza due to failures of the PV plant, with several periods throughout the day when energy production was 0 kWh.

2.2. Heatwave identification and severity

Heatwave windows were obtained from the official bulletins issued by the Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET) for Spain and the Instituto Português do Mar e da Atmosfera (IPMA) for Portugal, and two were selected per country for analysis which are shown in Table II.

TableII

In all analyses we define a pre period as the five days immediately preceding each agency-reported heatwave, and a post period as the five days immediately following it. For each plant and event, we also compute two within-window descriptors to summarise thermal severity: the maximum hourly 2-m air temperature (T_{\max}) and cumulative degree-hours above 35°C (DH35).

TableIII

For both Portugal and Spain, the first episode was harsher at every plant, combining higher peaks (T_{\max} up to 38.9°C in Spain, 39.4°C in Portugal) with longer thermal exposure (DH35 up to 39h in Spain, 26h in Portugal). Cross-country patterns hint at different stress modes: Spanish events show greater persistence (mean DH35 of 24h) while Portuguese plants reach higher temperatures (mean T_{\max} of 38.4°C), which may translate into endurance-driven efficiency losses versus peak-temperature risks.

2.3 ERA5-Land representativeness

ERA5-Land hourly air temperature and GHI are benchmarked against SIAR for the Amibil location for different regimes (pre, during and post heatwave) and for the two Spanish heatwaves, reporting r , mean absolute error (MAE), normalised mean bias error (NMBE) and normalised root mean squared error (NRMSE). Normalised metrics use the station mean as divisor. The goal is to quantify representativeness to support ERA5-Land use.

2.4 PVSyst simulations

Each plant is simulated in PVSyst (8.0.14) under two meteorological drivers: (i) a TMY design case using Meteonorm 8.2 (2000–2019), with site-specific horizon (Meteonorm web service) and a 3D scene for shading; and (ii) an actual-meteorology case, driven by ERA5-Land GHI and air temperature. Geometry, loss assumptions, shading and the AC boundary are identical across runs. Outputs are hourly simulated energies using the ERA5-Land and TMY data $E_{sim(ERA5),h}$ and $E_{sim(TMY),h}$, respectively. PR is computed at hourly and energy-weighted daily scales.

$$PR_{ERA5,h} = \frac{E_{real,h}}{E_{sim(ERA5),h}} \quad (1)$$

$$PR_{TMY,h} = \frac{E_{real,h}}{E_{sim(TMY),h}} \quad (2)$$

$$PR_{ERA5,d} = \frac{\sum_h E_{real,h}}{\sum_h E_{sim(ERA5),h}} \quad (3)$$

$$PR_{TMY,d} = \frac{\sum_h E_{real,h}}{\sum_h E_{sim(TMY),h}} \quad (4)$$

To characterise typical performance, a diurnal baseline from the 5-day pre-heatwave period was computed as the median PR by hour-of-day, $\tilde{P}R_{ERA5}^{BL}(h_d)$, and a daily baseline as the mean and standard deviation of the daily values for the same period (analogously for TMY). The mean relative difference between TMY and ERA5-Land daily baselines is also computed (Mean ΔPR_{rel}).

2.5 Resilience metrics

During each event, W , hourly anomalies relative to the ERA5-Land diurnal baseline for each site are computed,

$$\Delta PR_{ERA5,h} = PR_{ERA5,h}^W - \tilde{P}R_{ERA5}^{BL}(h_d) \quad (5)$$

and three event metrics are derived: (i) Drop magnitude (absolute and relative) at the minimum ΔPR ; (ii) time-to-trough (hours from heatwave start to that minimum); and (iii) recovery-to-90% (hours from the trough to the first time $PR_{ERA5,h}^W \geq 0.9\tilde{P}R_{ERA5}^{BL}(h_d)$). These metrics use ERA5-

Land in the denominator to keep meteorology explicit and isolate asset behaviour. The same metrics are computed for daily PR values.

The cumulative design-expectation gap is quantified with TMY as energy not served (ENS_{TMY}) reported in MWh, MWh/MWp and as a percentage of $\sum E_{sim(TMY)}$ over the event.

$$ENS_{TMY} = \sum_{h \in W} (E_{sim(TMY),h} - E_{real,h}) \quad (6)$$

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents an event-centred assessment and discussion of three Iberian PV plants across four agency-declared heatwaves.

3.1 Site-level validation: ERA5-Land vs in-situ

ERA5-Land hourly air temperature and GHI were benchmarked against a co-located station at the Amibil site, restricting validation to daylight hours (ERA5-Land GHI > 100W/m², Tables IV and V), showing strong agreement.

TableIV

TableV

For air temperature, correlations are high in all regimes, bias is essentially neutral throughout (NMBE between -0.16% and 0.39%) and MAE and NRMSE are small with the only notable exceptions being during and post-2S. In practice, a 2 to 3°C error translates to only around 1% instantaneous efficiency uncertainty for crystalline-Si (using typical 0.4-0.5%/°C), so temperature representation is adequate for PV performance modelling. For GHI, skill is very high (up to 0.984) and biases are small, but it is event and regime-dependent, with post-2S showing the weakest agreement.

Figures 2 and 3 also summarize the point-by-point agreement between ERA5-Land and the co-located station at Amibil across regimes. Air temperature clusters tightly around the 1:1 line, with most points inside the $\pm 10\%$ corridor consistent with the low MAE and NRMSE. GHI shows larger spread matching the larger NRMSE values and the degradation seen post-2S.

Figure2

Figure3

Figures 4 and 5 present a time-series view for 2S as an example. ERA5-Land reproduces the diurnal cycle and day-to-day variability of both variables. Temperature shows the expected smoothing of extremes (slightly lower daytime peaks and slightly higher nighttime lows), yet the timing is well aligned. GHI reproduces the diurnal cycle, with occasional amplitude differences on partly cloudy hours.

Figure4

Figure5

1
2
3 These results show a minimal temperature bias and small-to-moderate GHI bias which
4 indicate that ERA5-Land is representative and appropriate as the meteorological driver for the
5 PVsyst runs and as the reference in the PR-based event metrics.
6
7

8 **3.2. Baseline performance**

9 The baseline is the typical diurnal PR for each PV plant, computed from the pre-heatwave
10 window (ERA5-Land driven denominator). A baseline using a TMY-driven denominator is also
11 computed. Figure 6 shows the ERA5-Land baselines by hour of day, while Figure 7 shows the
12 hourly difference between baselines (TMY-ERA5-Land, in PR percentage points).
13

14 The ERA5-Land diurnal baselines reveal distinct operating signatures. Amibil maintains a high,
15 flat plateau around 95-98% across the solar peak, Ariza reaches an early maximum and then
16 drifts toward 90-95%, and Zebro operates systematically lower (80-90%) with a gradual
17 afternoon decline. These shapes frame the later event analysis by fixing the typical hourly
18 performance against which heat-stress anomalies are measured.
19

20 Figure 7 indicates that ERA5-Land and TMY baselines are broadly aligned at mid-day, with
21 the highest differences concentrated near sunrise and sunset. Because these hours yield less
22 energy, hourly differences translate only weakly to the daily-energy weighted PR.
23
24

25 Figure6

26
27 Figure7

28
29 Table VI reports daily, energy-weighted PR (mean \pm standard deviation, SD) for ERA5-Land
30 and TMY together with the relative mean difference. The ERA5-Land daily baselines are
31 internally consistent and narrow. Amibil centres near 95% with small dispersion, Ariza is
32 slightly lower but also has small dispersion and Zebro operates at lower levels (83-86%) with
33 broader dispersion reflecting its lower, more sloped diurnal shape. The hourly profile of the
34 baselines (Figure 7) suggests that offsets arise mainly at hours closer to sunrise and sunset,
35 hence their impact on daily, energy-weighted PR is limited but not negligible when deviations
36 are large (2S at Amibil and Zebro). Values above 100% arise because this index is defined as
37 observed energy divided by the TMY simulation for the same period. They simply indicate that
38 the TMY driver underestimates energy in the pre-window (mainly at low sun angles) and do
39 not imply physical PR above 100%.
40
41
42
43

44 TableVI

45 **3.3 Performance under heatwaves**

46 Performance during the events is assessed by hourly and daily PR anomalies relative to the
47 ERA5-Land based diurnal baseline from the pre-event window. Figures 8 through 13 show
48 these anomalies as well as the trough (largest negative anomaly) and the recovery-to-90%. In
49 Table VII resilience metrics are condensed for hourly and daily data. Large positive spikes at
50 sunrise/sunset reflect the relative anomaly definition at low-sun hours (small hourly
51 baseline/simulated energy), not physical PR >100%. These points have negligible energy
52 weight and do not affect daily metrics.
53
54
55
56

57 TableVII

58
59 Figure8

60

Figure9

Analysing Figures 8 and 9 and Table VII for Amibil, both events exhibit a classic heat-stress signature: troughs occur in the afternoon when module/inverter temperatures peak, followed by rapid recovery as thermal load eases. The deeper but shorter-lived shock in 1S is consistent with its higher thermal severity (Table III), likely reflecting brief protective derating near the peak and quick restoration as temperatures fall. In 2S, the trough occurs at 17:00 UTC with 1 hour of daylight remaining; because our evaluation uses daylight-only hours, the reported recovery-to-90% includes the overnight gap and should not be interpreted as a slower physical response. Amibil's flat, high midday baseline means sunrise/sunset anomalies carry reduced energy weight, so large hourly excursions compress into small daily deficits. At the daily scale, both events show single-digit drops that peak on day 4 (1S) and day 2 (2S) and recover within the same day, indicating that heat-related risk is concentrated in a handful of hot afternoon hours rather than sustained multi-day degradation.

Figure10

Figure11

Ariza's response mirrors its baseline signature (early peak followed by an afternoon drift) with PR anomalies clustering near zero for much of the window but having extreme values in mid-afternoon, when thermal load and inverter temperatures are highest. In 1S, the drop is moderate and short-lived, with an almost immediate rebound once the peak passes, which is consistent with brief protective derating rather than sustained loss. By contrast, 2S shows a deeper trough and a slower intra-day recovery, even though its thermal severity is lower (Table III). This inversion suggests that factors such as inverter derating thresholds, transient curtailment, or weaker convective cooling, dominated over meteorology in determining the depth and duration of the dip. At the daily scale, losses remain single-digit and short-lived (Table VII), reinforcing that risk at Ariza is hour-centric, concentrated in hot afternoon hours rather than a multi-day decline.

Figure12

Figure13

Zebro behaves in line with its sloping afternoon baseline. In 1P, Zebro's hourly anomaly has a convex diurnal shape, slightly positive at midday and negative towards sunrise/sunset, while the hourly trough occurs late afternoon and resolves within 3h. Because the negative hours coincide with low irradiance, the daily aggregate does not turn negative during the heatwave period († in Table VII marks the daily minimum just after the heatwave). In 2P, however, the trough occurs near solar noon, carries high energy weight, and translates into a daily drop on day 1 with recovery the next day. Thus, at Zebro the deficit is not systematically midday centred.

Across the three plants the response is hour-centric (sharp troughs with intra-day recovery), but the magnitude and day-level impact depend on each site's baseline and on when within the diurnal cycle the minimum occurs. The intra-day drops and recoveries observed even in the post-heatwave regimes indicate that the proximate driver of hourly PR deficits is not the

label “heatwave” per se, but short-lived exceedance of thermal thresholds (high air temperature with limited wind cooling) that triggers protective derating and then normalisation once thermal load eases. This is consistent with PV temperature physics, where module temperature responds to irradiance, ambient temperature, and wind speed, and with evidence that inverters thermally derate under high component/ambient temperatures, hence acute afternoon spikes can produce the same signature inside or outside officially declared heatwaves.

3.4 TMY design gap

Table VIII quantifies the energy not served when TMY is used as the driver, i.e., the energy that TMY-based design would expect but was not delivered in operation. In all cases these values are non-zero, but their magnitude and timing vary widely across plants. In absolute terms and per-kWp the largest gaps occur at Zebro-2P, Amibil-1S and Amibil-2S. As a share of simulated energy, the largest relative shortfall is Ariza-2S, followed by Zebro-2P and Amibil-2S. The regime split is also site and heatwave dependent. During event losses dominate at Amibil-1S, Zebro-1P and Zebro-2P while post-event losses are the largest component for Amibil-2S and Ariza-2S. This indicates that TMY-only simulations can overestimate both during and, in some cases, after the event.

Within this limited sample (three plants, four events), the data show that the size and timing of the TMY gap are plant-specific and event-specific, reinforcing the need to complement TMY with event-centred analyses when assessing operational risk.

Table VIII

4. Conclusion

Photovoltaic energy is an essential tool to decarbonize energy systems and mitigate climate change, however PV plants are vulnerable to extreme events such as heatwaves. This study analyses the impact of heatwaves on three PV plants in the Iberian Peninsula, a region known to have a high PV potential, and is particularly exposed to climate change. An event-centric assessment of PV operational resilience under heatwaves was performed, pairing observed energy production with ERA5-Land and TMY PVsyst simulations for these plants and four heatwave episodes.

ERA5-Land reproduced site meteorology well at the validated site (air-temperature $r = 0.91$ - 0.95 ; GHI up to 0.98), supporting its use as the denominator for PR-based metrics.

Pre-event PR baselines revealed distinct operating signatures (flat and high values at Amibil, early-peak and afternoon drifts at Ariza and lower sloping values at Zebro) that shaped event responses.

Across events, impacts were hour-centric: sharp hourly troughs with intra-day recovery (deepest hourly drop 90.44% at Amibil-1S), while the largest daily loss was 17.59% (Zebro-2P) with recovery within 0-1 days. If the troughs happen near sunrise or sunset, those hours yield little energy, so the daily impact is small (e.g., Zebro-1P). If they happen around solar noon, when most energy is produced, even a short drop can translate into a large daily loss (e.g., Zebro-2P).

TMY expectations overestimated energy in all cases (ENS non-zero), with the largest absolute gap at Zebro-2P (553.25 kWh; 36.88 kWh/kWp; 17.3% of simulated energy) and the highest relative gap at Ariza-2S (22.34% of simulated energy). Intra-day drops and recoveries were

also observed outside official heatwave windows, indicating that brief exceedances of thermal thresholds, even if not in the context of a heatwave, drive operational risk.

These findings are bounded by our scope (three plants, four events, in-situ validation at one-site) and compare stationary TMY 2000-2019 against 2024-2025 conditions. Even within these limitations, the message for European planning of photovoltaics is clear: plant resilience must be treated as a core criterion. In a climate context, anthropogenic global warming is increasing the frequency, intensity, and duration of hot extremes, expanding the number of hours that exceed operational thermal thresholds; consequently, although PV losses concentrate in brief hot-afternoon windows, those high-risk hours will occur more often, including outside periods officially declared as heatwaves, across Europe. TMY should be complemented with event-centric stress tests driven by reanalysis or site-calibrated data, and O&M should target hot-hour risk inside and outside heatwaves (thermal derating management, ventilation/filters, spares readiness).

In the future, resilience assessment should be scaled both geographically and temporally, integrate CMIP6/CORDEX projections to quantify future hot-hour frequencies, and fuse reanalysis with SCADA/inverter logs and on-site wind and module temperature to sharpen attribution and uncertainty, using these metrics in procurement, design reviews and operational dashboards to make PV plants measurably more robust in a warming planet.

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Figure 1 - Location of the PV powerplants. Source: Authors own work.

145x100mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2 - Direct comparison between measured and ERA5-Land air temperature for both heatwaves and for each regime. Source: Authors own work

96x84mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 3 - Direct comparison between measured and ERA5-Land GHI for both heatwaves and for each regime. Source: Authors own work

96x84mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 4 - Measured (blue) and ERA5-Land (orange) air temperature during S2. Source: Authors own work.

147x43mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 5 - Measured (blue) and ERA5-Land (orange) GHI during S2. Source: Authors own work.

147x43mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 6 - ERA5-Land PR baseline for each PV plant. Source: Authors own work.

137x87mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 7 - Differences between TMY and ERA5-Land baselines for each PV plant. Source: Authors own work.

138x86mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 8 - PR anomalies during and post 1S for Amibil. Source: Authors own work.

118x85mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 9 - PR anomalies during and post 2S for Amibil. Source: Authors own work.

119x86mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 10 - PR anomalies during and post 1S for Ariza. Source: Authors own work.

119x86mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 11 - PR anomalies during and post 2S for Ariza. Source: Authors own work.

119x86mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 12 - PR anomalies during and post 1P for Zebro. Source: Authors own work.

119x86mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Figure 13 - PR anomalies during and post 1P for Zebro. Source: Authors own work.

120x86mm (300 x 300 DPI)

ID	Name	Installed capacity (kWp)	PV modules	Inverters	Mounting	Tilt (°)	Azimuth (°)
1	Zebro	37.06	JAM72S30 545/MR (545 Wp)	SUN2000 40KTL M3 (x1)	ground-mounted elevated structure	18°	-30°
2	Ariza	15	JAM66S30/MR (500 Wp)	SUN2000 6KTL L1 (x2)	ground-mounted	20	10°
3	Amibil	64.5	TRINA SOLAR Vertex S+ (R) (430 Wp)	SUN2000 KTL M3 36 kW (x1) SUN2000 KTL M5 17 kW (x1)	rooftop-mounted	20	-13°

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Heatwave ID	Country	Start	End	Source
1S	Spain	23 July 2024	1 August 2024	(AEMET, 2024)
2S	Spain	28 June 2025	30 June 2025	(AEMET, 2025)
1P	Portugal	15 August 2024	21 August 2024	(IPMA, 2024)
2P	Portugal	24 May 2025	1 June 2025	(IPMA, 2025)

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Power plant and Heatwave ID	T _{max} (°C)	DH35 (h)
Amibil_1S	38.9	39
Ariza_1S	37.5	33
Amibil_2S	36.2	13
Ariza_2S	35.9	11
Zebro_1P	39.4	26
Zebro_2P	37.4	16

Regime	Heatwave	r	NMBE (%)	NRMSE (%)	MAE (°C)
Pre-heatwave	1S	0.938	0.10	10.65	2.26
	2S	0.935	0.12	10.75	2.32
Heatwave	1S	0.912	0.02	9.29	2.01
	2S	0.949	0.39	12.52	3.07
Post-heatwave	1S	0.945	-0.16	8.36	1.72
	2S	0.837	0.29	12.68	2.46

Regime	Heatwave	r	NMBE (%)	NRMSE (%)	MAE (W/m ²)
Pre-heatwave	1S	0.974	8.58	21.68	48.32
	2S	0.920	0.30	33.37	59.90
Heatwave	1S	0.948	10.42	31.63	57.18
	2S	0.964	-1.21	23.08	58.48
Post-heatwave	1S	0.984	5.55	16.13	38.77
	2S	0.840	-1.86	59.64	126.83

Power plant	Heatwave	ERA5-Land Mean \pm SD (%)	TMY Mean \pm SD (%)	Mean ΔPR_{rel} (%)
Amibil	1S	95.38 \pm 6.41	93.15 \pm 3.27	-2.34
	2S	94.64 \pm 2.12	122.03 \pm 40.96	28.94
Ariza	1S	94.07 \pm 6.35	97.31 \pm 12.61	3.44
	2S	88.55 \pm 3.84	82.84 \pm 5.19	-6.44
Zebro	1P	86.34 \pm 14.72	89.41 \pm 13.59	3.56
	2P	82.60 \pm 9.51	97.67 \pm 30.47	18.24

Power plant		Amibil		Ariza		Zebro	
Heatwave		1S	2S	1S	2S	1P	2P
Hourly	Drop _{max} (%)	90.44	63.83	49.52	70.86	20.85	80.31
	Drop _{max,rel} (%)	93.58	60.8	53.29	78.37	31.61	88.85
	Hour of trough (UTC)	14:00	17:00	16:00	15:00	18:00	12:00
	Time-to-trough (h)	110	65	88	63	90	12
	Recovery-to-90% (h)	3	13	1	3	41	3
Daily	Drop _{max} (%)	7.55	3.81	6.5	9.99	1.21 [†]	17.59
	Drop _{max,rel} (%)	7.95	3.96	6.99	10.72	1.29 [†]	21.72
	Time-to-trough (d)	4	2	9	2	7 [†]	0
	Recovery-to-90% (d)	0	0	0	1	0 [†]	1

Power plant	Heatwave	During heatwave			Post-heatwave			Total		
		kWh	kWh/kWp	% of E _{sim}	kWh	kWh/kWp	% of E _{sim}	kWh	kWh/kWp	% of E _{sim}
Amibil	1S	414.54	27.64	11.29	83.23	5.55	4.21	497.77	33.18	8.81
	2S	68.02	4.53	5.24	399.57	26.64	18.29	467.58	31.17	13.43
Ariza	1S	59.02	3.93	8.51	59.09	3.94	12.94	118.11	7.87	10.27
	2S	65.91	4.39	21.4	108.18	7.21	22.96	174.09	11.6	22.34
Zebro	1P	206.19	13.74	13.42	56.52	3.77	5.21	262.70	17.51	10.02
	2P	342.99	22.87	15.94	210.26	14.02	20.07	553.25	36.88	17.30